

Farm Tank - A Business Model To Connect Smallholder Farmers To The Global Market

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Abstract

Farm Tank is a startup business model that aims to revolutionize the global agricultural market by creating a unified platform for farmers to connect with buyers and regulators to streamline the process of farming, selling, and distributing agricultural products at a global scale. The goal of Farm Tank is to create a system that will provide farmers with the necessary tools and resources to compete on a global scale, while also improving the sustainability and efficiency of the agricultural industry. The platform will enable farmers to connect with buyers from around the world, providing them with access to a much larger market than they would have had otherwise. This will increase demand for their products and provide them with the opportunity to earn higher profits.

Keywords: Agriculture, Farmers, Market, Website, Pricing, Distribution

Introduction

The agricultural industry has been facing numerous challenges for decades, including a lack of access to markets, limited access to financing, and difficulties in navigating complex regulatory frameworks [1]. Furthermore, climate change, declining soil fertility, and water scarcity have added to the challenges of modern farming. These challenges have led to a fragmented and inefficient agricultural industry, where many farmers struggle to make ends meet [2]. The Farm Tank model strives to tackle these issues by bridging the information gap between buyers and sellers, enhancing process efficiency across interconnected markets, and promoting real-time price discovery based on current demand and supply, all aimed at enhancing uniformity in farm marketing. We promote agricultural transactions through our digital platform and network of service partners. Farm Tank offers solutions for product quality checks, end-to-end logistical services, and online payments between buyers and sellers. Farm Tank's ultimate aim is to increase farmers' profit and provide all services in need for farmers seamlessly. And the consumers also get benefitted since the portal price is less than the market price, they save money and also get quality products and services delivered to their doorstep. At the same time, the platform will also help to regulate the demands in the market. By providing real-time information on supply and demand, Farm Tank will enable farmers to adjust their production accordingly.

This will help to prevent oversupply and undersupply of agricultural products, ensuring that prices remain stable.

Another key aspect of the Farm Tank platform is its ability to solve growing and distribution issues. Through the use of advanced technology, the platform will provide farmers with access to the latest farming techniques and tools. This will help farmers to improve their yields, reduce waste, and increase efficiency. Furthermore, the platform will also provide farmers with access to a network of distributors and logistics providers, making it easier for them to get their products to market.

One of the main benefits of the Farm Tank platform is its ability to improve sustainability in the agricultural industry. By providing farmers with access to the latest technologies and techniques, the platform will help to reduce the environmental impact of farming. This will involve the implementation of precision farming techniques that aim to decrease the utilization of fertilizers and pesticides, and adopting advanced irrigation methods to minimize water consumption.

The Farm Tank platform will be built on advanced technology, including artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things. These technologies will enable the platform to provide real-time data on supply and demand and help optimize farming techniques and logistics. To achieve its goals, Farm Tank will need to partner with a wide range of stakeholders, including farmers, buyers, regulators, financial institutions, logistics providers, and technology companies. By bringing together these stakeholders, Farm Tank aims to create a more efficient and sustainable agricultural industry, one that benefits all participants. Overall, Farm Tank is an innovative startup that has the potential to transform the agricultural industry. By creating a unified platform for farmers to connect with buyers and regulators, Farm Tank will help to solve some of the key challenges facing modern farming[3].

Figure 1. Company logo for Farm Tank

Overview of the company

The Farm Tank platform will benefit buyers and regulators by providing them with access to a more transparent and efficient agricultural market. Buyers will be able to connect with farmers from around the world, providing them with access to a wider range of products at competitive prices. Regulators will also benefit from the platform, as it will enable them to monitor the agricultural market more closely, ensuring that farmers are complying with regulatory requirements and standards.

In addition to these benefits, Farm Tank will also provide farmers with access to financing and other resources. The platform will collaborate with financial institutions to allow farmers to obtain loans and other financial products that can aid in farm investments and enhance their productivity. Additionally, the platform will offer educational resources and training opportunities to farmers, empowering them to enhance their farming expertise and knowledge.

Company Title

Farm Tank: a website to bridge the farmers of India and create a unified website to connect smallholder farmers to the global market

A description of service:

Farmers can benefit from a user-friendly platform that generates market opportunities. The platform offers unrestricted access to a global market from any location at any time. It facilitates negotiation, contract generation and provides transparent and reliable market information. Integrated and secure payment procedures are available on the platform. Customized logistical and product quality assurance services are provided. The marketplace ensures that all buyers and vendors are legitimate.

Mission statement

Buy and sell agricultural products online (buyers meet farmers) to increase the value of Agricultural products by selling them directly to customers without middlemen. India undoubtedly has one of the largest agricultural marketplaces in the world, which makes it crucial to have a service that can link farmers across the nation. Selling their products at a higher price where farmers receive the highest price, would assist them in maximizing their profits [4].

Vision statement

The longevity of the platform, Transparency, fair price, user-friendly, 24/7 availability and an easy-to-use checkout are all our business philosophies. Our goal is to minimize the imbalance of information between buyers and sellers, improve the efficiency of processes across interconnected markets, and facilitate real-time price discovery based on current demand and supply to promote consistency in farm marketing. We aspire to aid farmers in earning equitable revenue.

Company goals

Farm Tank platform for farmers can deliver e-commerce organic products marketplace produce to consumers using a modest price to have the products transported to the consumers.

Market research and analysis of top market players must be done: Prominent farmer's marketplaces are Farmdrop, Faarmbox Direct and Our Harvest, etc.

Must know revenue channels - "How to earn from online farmer's marketplace": The online farmer's market has 4 revenue channels: Commission on each transaction, Commission on each delivery, Marketplace ads, Subscription.

Must know "How it works: A prior well-designed plan"

Figure 2. Work Plan for Farm Tank

Industry

We will make a website called Farm Tank platform for farmers which provides service to farmers and also raises profit for farmers. It enables farmers to connect directly to consumers through our website. We provide a lot of information like daily wagers locations, predict the Demand for crops so that farmers will cultivate the crop which is expected to be in demand in near future.

We aim to give comparative information on low-interest rates by the banks, and a lot more. We will update our app on a day-to-day basis like the price of fruits, vegetables and the quantity. It connects farmers directly to us. We can view this app from two perspectives, one is the service that we provide to farmers and the other is the profit we get from the services we provide. Farmers have added the privilege to sign in through an Aadhaar card and modify their account as they wish through our website.

The platform is divided into 2 sections - Services and Profits. In Services we provide a lot of information like daily wagers locations, the demand of crops, information on low-interest rates by the banks, giving detailed information about government schemes, providing farmers fertilizers and pesticides at low prices and voice assistant or change of language etc. While coming to profits we can buy products in bulk and sell to farmers at low costs and get subsidies from the government, we can lease lands from the farmers and cultivate crops and, and we can be middlemen between grocery stores and farmers. In this way, we and the farmers both get benefits [5].

Technical marketing activities like SEO can be considered for start-up businesses, whereas other activities like an advertisement and offers stay common for all businesses depending on targeted customers and budget [6].

Legal structure

Most farmers worldwide face a cycle of low market orientation, investment, risk-taking capacity, production, value creation, and earnings due to a lack of effective market access and severe market linkages, which compel them to rely on middlemen for sales, resulting in meager returns [5]. To help farmers obtain better prices, we aim to use the internet and mobile phones to create direct market connections between farmers and consumers, eliminating middlemen and ensuring payments at the farm gate.

In terms of company structure, founders take the same risk by leaving their current roles, while actual employees are in the second layer, hired after receiving consumer revenue, and later employees are in the third layer [7]. The founders should hold about 50% of the company, with subsequent layers having equal shares of about 10%, split among everyone in the layer, and a preference for equal splits with friends instead of insisting on owning more [8].

The first actual employees are in the second stratum. By the time we recruit this layer, we should already have money coming in from consumers, whichever comes first. Since they were paid from day one and, in all honesty, didn't start the company, they joined it as an employee, these people didn't assume as much risk [9]. Later employees make up the third stratum. The business was doing fairly well by the time they joined [10].

The founders should end up with about 50% of the company, in total. Each of the next five layers should end up with about 10% of the company, split equally among everyone in the layer. We would always rather split a new company 50-50 with a friend than insist on owning 60% [11].

Key Competitors:

National Agriculture Market ([eNam](#)), KisanMandi Online Agri market Private Limited ([KisanMandi.com](#)), Krishi-Market , Small Farms, AgriMarket Place , mKisan, AgriBros

Products & Services

User Profile & Registration. Customers can create an account on the grocery delivery app using their email, social media accounts, or phone number as per their choice.

Customer Feedback & Review. The grocery delivery app allows customers to provide feedback and reviews on products, which can help others feel more confident while making their first purchase.

Search Option. The app's search feature enables customers to search for products based on their preferred category, brand, and price range.

Delivery Tracking. The grocery delivery app offers real-time tracking of delivery details, such as order arrival, to customers.

Order Management. Customers can manage their orders, including placing or canceling them and replacing items, without having to go through the entire product list again.

Multiple Payment Options. The app provides various payment options, including COD, credit/debit cards, and digital payments, allowing customers to shop without worrying about cash availability.

Schedule Delivery. Customers can schedule the delivery of their orders at their convenience, depending on their busy schedules.

Products:

Our goal is to become the most reliable retailer where both employees and customers enjoy their experience. We plan to achieve this by prioritizing our customers and investing in our stores, employees, and channels to provide the best shopping experience possible[13].

An agricultural product, such as wheat, corn, or soybeans, or a type of livestock, such as cattle, hogs, sheep, horses, or chickens, utilized or generated in farming activities, is referred to as a "farm product," as is a byproduct of such a crop or animal in its unprocessed stage (such as ginned cotton, wool-clip, maple syrup)[14].

Our store offers an extensive selection of products, which includes packaged snacks, fresh produce, food grains, oils, spices, and beverages, among others. We stock over 1,000 items from 400 various brands to cater to our customers' diverse needs. Through our online platform, customers can conveniently place their grocery orders, and our team will ensure their delivery right to their doorstep [15].

Services:

All types of users can log in safely. Voice support, Low-cost insecticides and fertilizers are available. Farmer subsidies are offered to lease a farmer's land for crop cultivation, All selection with simply one click [16]. Fresh produce is supplied by more than 5000 farmers at Mandi prices. fresh vegetables Next day delivery to your door. GST bill, available in print and electronic versions for filing returns. Organize our payment options (bill pay is also available through our app). View our house and auto insurance proof of coverage [17]. Give the ease of using your mobile device to manage your insurance coverage anytime, anywhere. The application contains detailed information on the prices of various commodities such as corn, wheat, soybean, canola, live cattle, lean hogs, and other related items [18]. Finally, we are working on a mobile application. It will benefit both our users and our operations and administrative staff for the benefit of all countries and farmers [19]. We believe in Service and

The problem this startup addresses:

Gives farmers accurate information regarding price ranges across India - through our app, farmers are taught farming expertise. Farmers can sell their products to us [20]. Our customers receive fresh food on their doorsteps so they may spend time with their families. Farmers can learn about the various interest rates that banks are willing to give [21].

Proprietary features that give a competitive advantage:

This is a combination of farmers' apps along with the grocery app like big basket etc. The above-mentioned services give us a far advantage to compete with us. We are cost-effective, flexible, environmentally friendly, and simple to use. Rather than profiting from our organization, we try to make farmers profitable. We design in as many languages as possible. No need to worry about prices as farmers get more of the amount in their initial sales. Low subscription rates for the farmers to subscribe to our app [22].

Business Name	Farm Tank
Product/Service	<i>To enhance consistency in farm marketing, it is crucial to remove the information disparity between purchasers and suppliers, simplify processes across unified markets, and encourage immediate price discovery based on the current supply and demand situation [23]. At Farm Tank, we facilitate agricultural transactions using our digital platform and network of service partners. We provide end-to-end logistical services, conduct product quality checks, and enable online payments for both buyers and sellers [24].</i>
Special Benefits	<i>Curbside pickup of productivity needs at a reasonable price reliable, confirmed data gathered from experts, used by the sales hub to boost income. Agents stationed in different areas will intervene and go directly to farmers to provide guidance [25]. After careful examination by agents, we will lease idle agricultural property for the advantage of the company, employ labourers (who are looking for work) to enter the leased area and cultivate crops, and provide 24/7 online chat support that provides guidance. Analyzing the loan interest rates that various institutions are offering. greater access to government services [26]. Using the Aadhar card number to identify your enthusiasm for farmers to use contemporary technology. interpreters and voice aid. The system interface was made simpler.</i>
Unique Features	<i>The above-mentioned services give us a far advantage to compete with us. We are cost-effective, flexible, environmentally friendly, and simple to use. Rather than profiting from our organisation we try to make farmers profitable to We design in as many languages as possible. No need to worry about prices as farmers get more than the amount in their initial sales[27]. We provide pesticides at low rates. Low subscription rates to the farmers to subscribe to our app The application contains detailed information on the prices of various commodities such as corn, wheat, soybean, canola, live cattle, lean hogs, and other related items[28].</i>

Limits and Liabilities	<i>Hard to change the farmers from selling their products to middlemen to us, gaining their trust. Managing the users and the sellers. In times if there is a shortage of products, we need to manage the requirements of the user's[29]. Effective coordination must be in the team if not the updates from the ground level to high would be difficult. Improper results in stock price.</i>
Production and Delivery	<i>The business announces the app's formal debut and begins delivering predetermined numbers of orders to each dealer. The sales department then uses dealers to research market demand. A new production schedule is unveiled in accordance with supply and demand[30].</i>
Suppliers	<i>Farm Tank has a huge supply of products from different farmers across the country and the Farmers of India join our hands to make this app a better place.</i>
Intellectual Property Special Permits	<i>The UPOV Convention is a sui generis regime of intellectual property protection especially adapted to protect the plant breeding industries of the developed world[31], copyrights and design patents known as moral rights. Indigenous intellectual property, Plant breeder's rights[32]</i>

Product/Service	<i>We provide a wide range of goods, including packaged snacks, fresh fruits, vegetables. All types of users can log in safely. Voice support, Low-cost insecticides and fertilisers are available. Farmer subsidies are offered. Leasing a farmer's land for crop cultivation, All selection with simply one click. Fresh produce is supplied from more than 5000 farmers at Mandi prices. fresh vegetables [33].</i>
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Table 1. Product & Service Description Worksheet

Marketing Plan

This section of the plan outlines information on our industry, competitors, target market, and strategies to market your business to those customers[36].

Market research

As an agricultural startup, Farm Tank has conducted extensive market research to understand the competitive landscape and identify its target market. The research revealed that there is a need for a digital platform that eliminates information asymmetry between buyers and sellers and streamlines procedures across integrated markets to increase uniformity in farm marketing. Farm Tank's target market is farmers, buyers, and sellers in the agricultural industry who are looking for a convenient, reliable, and efficient way to conduct agricultural transactions[37].

Target customer

Farm Tank, a platform created to help farmers and market managers launch their own multi-producer internet markets. This platform can be used to display items, take payments, interact with consumers, and replicate a real farmer's market. It can also only be open for a limited period of time. Consumers (buyers) primarily using the online portal will tend to be married females at higher income levels, individuals with strong diet or health concerns, and individuals who are supportive of local farming and agriculture open space. Daily wagers whose agricultural land has turned uneconomic and who are in search of a job even when he/she has enough knowledge of agricultural activities [39]. Agents who have enough technical, practical and agricultural knowledge will be recruited.

Marketing our product/service

We can advertise our application in the following ways: Television, Newspapers, Magazines, Public relations, Multimedia, and Social media marketing.

To market its business to these customers, Farm Tank will use various digital marketing channels such as social media, email marketing, and search engine optimization to reach potential customers. The company will also attend agricultural trade shows and events to establish a physical presence and build relationships with potential customers. Additionally, Farm Tank will leverage its network of service partners to spread the word about its platform and encourage adoption among their customers[40].

Based on the competitive analysis worksheet, FarmTank has several strengths, including eNAM's established presence in the Indian agricultural market and large user base, FarmTank's innovative approach of combining technology with agricultural practices, its user-friendly interface, and the potential for a powerful partnership between eNAM and FarmTank. However, FarmTank also faces several weaknesses, such as eNAM's lack of global recognition, competition from established agricultural technology platforms, difficulty in establishing itself in markets where eNAM is not established, and dependence on effective collaboration between eNAM and FarmTank.

Business Model Canvas

Figure 3. Business Model Canvas for Farm Tank

Promotional budget

Deciding the promotional budget for an agricultural startup like Farm Tank requires careful consideration of various factors. The company's marketing goals, target audience, competitive landscape, and available resources all play a crucial role in determining the appropriate promotional budget. Additionally, the type of promotional activities and the channels used, such as social media, events, or advertisements, also impact the budget. It is important to allocate resources effectively to ensure maximum impact on the target audience while also optimizing return on investment. Farm Tank may need to conduct market research to determine the most effective promotional strategies for reaching and engaging their target audience, and then allocate resources accordingly to achieve their marketing goals [41].

Distribution channels

These may include - Retail, direct sales, e-commerce, wholesale, inside sales force, outside sales representatives, OEMs [42]

	Distribution Channel (Farmer to Consumers)
Ease of Entry	This is only limited to authorized people
Geographic Proximity	The geographic proximity will be less as the goods will be taken from the nearby agriland. In case it is high, its payment will be added.
Costs	Cost will be packaging, transport
Management Experience	Since this is a direct distribution-based service, management of goods, manpower, training, and planning will be monitored from the beginning.
Staffing Capabilities	Since this involves the usage of people talented in the necessary sectors (Like how farmers are skilled in farming), no extra teaching or managing of employers will be necessary [43].
Marketing Needs	Since this will receive support from farmers, just an ample amount of marketing and advertising will be needed. (As people are already knowledgeable with Swiggy, Zomato, etc).

Table 2. Distribution Channel Assessment Worksheet

Operational Plan

This section explains the daily operation of your business, including its location, equipment, personnel and processes of our project Farm Tank [44].

Production. The Farm Tank Business involves activities such as production, services, purchasing of inputs, and marketing products with the objective of earning a profit.

Quality control. Business development includes various aspects such as product development, quality control, cost control, organizational development, marketing, and sector-specific skills. It encompasses both strategic and operational aspects.

Location. In this section, a location map can be incorporated into the plan to showcase the area of operation and the location of the FPO office. Providing an overview of the project area can help readers better understand the area of operations and the intended impact [45].

Legal environment. The legal environment, nature of the operation, and possible areas of improvement can be taken into consideration while designing the offering. Better the offering, the better the Customer Value Proposition (CVP).

Personnel. Farm Tank requires a minimum of 4 members who should possess fundamental knowledge about software engineering, web technologies, and databases. They need to have expertise in web development, coding and databases. Freelance professionals are preferred for the job [46].

Biographies

The majority of Indian agriculture is made up of numerous small and marginal farmers, accounting for around 85% of land holdings [47]. Due to their unorganized nature, these farmers struggle to obtain fair prices for their produce. However, SFAC, NABARD, and other organizations have implemented pilots that demonstrate organizing these farmers into Producer Organizations (POs) can significantly mitigate their issues [48]. By forming a PO, member farmers can benefit from economies of scale when purchasing inputs, processing and marketing their produce, as well as gain access to timely and adequate credit and links to markets [49]. The CEO of the FPO can work with various stakeholders, including progressive farmers, the FPO board, KVK scientists, and NGO members in the village, to determine the selection criteria and their ranking. However, not all criteria selected will be of equal importance in deciding which value chains to analyze [50].

E-Commerce Business

Farmer Tank is an e-commerce app aimed to provide direct service between the farmers and consumers. This acts as a middleman in the process of agricultural foods transaction, providing maximum profit to both farmers and consumers[51].

This business plan provides farm-grown vegetables directly to the hands of consumers which were taken proper care of all along the process of its cultivation. Once the consumer places their order in our “Farmer Tank” app, the specific product is collected from a nearby farm of “Farmer’s Tank” and packed diligently in an eco-friendly way and provided to the customer. The products will be sold only in our official online platform “Farmer Tank”, there won’t be any other platform providing “Farmer Tank” services and its products[52].

Technology	Providers
Web hosting service	Google website hosting
Web design service	web.com
Shopping cart provider	3dcart
Payment processing service	Helcim
Fulfillment & shipping services	WareIQ
Email marketing services	Mail Get Bolt

Table 3. Distribution Channel Assessment Worksheet

This Start-up differs from other platforms in various ways:

Cost-effective curbside pickup of productivity needs. Trustworthy data from professionals that have been validated. Sales hub to increase revenue. Agents in various regions will jump into the picture and directly visit farmers to guide them. For the company’s benefit, we will lease unused agricultural lands (after thorough inspection by agents) and employ laborers (who are in search of jobs) into leased lands and cultivate crops. A 24/7 online chat service that offers direction, evaluation of loan interest rates offered by different banks, more accessibility to government programs, Aadhar card number-based distinctive identification, farmers' eagerness to utilize modern technology, voice assistance and translators, simplified system interface.

Immediate goals and next steps

The immediate step would be to search for an investor and start the business with well-planned goals and objectives like creating an online platform for farmers, laborers, buyers, and agents to tie up on the web. A sales contract agreement must be made. Government license and approval must be obtained. Traceability with blockchain must be made sure. Logistics and transportation of products must be arranged.

Long-term goals and next steps

Transparency. Maintaining direct transactions between farmers and industry/retail with receipts

Fairtrade. The distribution of benefits in the supply chain is altered to the advantage of both the producers and purchasers involved.

User friendly. Lower expenses for buyers while maintaining dependability, and ensure that voice aid and translation services are available to benefit users who are unable to read.

Traceability. Crop reliability through supply chain traceability

Discussion

Farm Tank is a startup model that connects farmers and helps them share knowledge and collaborate on initiatives to address challenges in the farming industry. It reduces global farming disparities by leveling the playing field and providing access to resources and information for all farmers. Additionally, it promotes sustainable farming practices to address critical issues such as climate change and food security, while also reducing waste and promoting biodiversity [53]. By sharing knowledge and expertise, Farm Tank helps farmers learn about innovative approaches to farming that can ensure food availability for everyone, regardless of their location or economic situation. Overall, Farm Tank has the potential to be a game-changer

for farmers around the world, promoting sustainability and creating a more equitable and sustainable food system for all.

Conclusion

Building a unified global market for farmers is an important goal for ensuring global food security, reducing poverty, and promoting economic growth. We as biotechnologists can play a crucial role in supporting this effort by developing new crop varieties, improving farming practices, and addressing food safety and quality issues. By developing new crop varieties that are better adapted to different climates and soils, we can help farmers in different regions of the world to increase their productivity and compete more effectively in global markets. Biotechnologists can also help develop more efficient and sustainable farming practices that can reduce costs and improve yields[54].

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